

IMPLEMENTATION OF TEACHER COMPETENCY IMPROVEMENT PROGRAM IN KUNINGAN REGENCY IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Improving teacher competence is a key factor in improving the quality of education. This study aims to analyze the implementation of teacher competence improvement programs in Kuningan Regency, identify supporting and inhibiting factors, and assess the effectiveness of the program on the quality of learning. This study uses a qualitative descriptive approach with data collection methods through in-depth interviews, observations, and documentation studies. The subjects of the study involved elementary, junior high, and high school teachers who had participated in training and certification programs. Data were analyzed using the Miles and Huberman interactive analysis model, which includes data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions. The results of the study indicate that the teacher competency improvement program in Kuningan Regency has been running well, especially in terms of planning and implementing technology-based training and blended learning approaches. This program improves teachers' abilities in designing innovative learning, implementing technology in the classroom, and improving pedagogical skills and professionalism. However, there are obstacles in its implementation, such as limited infrastructure, diverse teacher motivations, and limited implementation time. To overcome these obstacles, the proposed strategies include improving school infrastructure, providing incentives for award teachers, stopping training time, and strengthening teacher working groups (KKG) and subject teacher deliberations (MGMP). The implication of this study is the importance of the desire for more adaptive education programs and policies to support optimal teacher competence.

Keywords : Implementation program , competency teacher , district Brass , upgrade quality of education ,

INTRODUCTION

Education serves as a fundamental pillar in achieving sustainable national development, with teachers playing a central role as facilitators, mentors, and role models in the learning process. The competence of teachers is critical not only for delivering academic content but also for guiding and inspiring students to reach their full potential. As such, improving teacher competence is essential to ensuring a high-quality, competitive education system.

In response to this need, the local government of Kuningan Regency in West Java has implemented a variety of programs aimed at enhancing teacher competence. These include competency-based training sessions, thematic workshops, mentoring to support curriculum implementation, and teacher certification initiatives. The goal is to develop four key areas of competence—pedagogical, professional, social, and personal—as outlined in Law Number 14 of 2005 on Teachers and Lecturers.

These efforts are further supported by regional regulations, such as the Kuningan Regent Regulation No. 69 of 2021, which highlights the strategic plan for strengthening teacher quality through professional development and the integration of technology in education. More recently, the "My Cool School" initiative, formalized through the Regent's Decree and official circulars, emphasizes teacher development through platforms like the "Teacher's House"—a dedicated space for learning, collaboration, and professional growth.

Despite these positive steps, the implementation of these programs is not without challenges. Resource limitations, including budget constraints and insufficient educational infrastructure, often hinder program effectiveness. Moreover, disparities between urban and rural schools create unequal access to training opportunities and modern educational tools, leaving many rural teachers at a disadvantage when it comes to applying new teaching methods or adopting the Merdeka Belajar Curriculum.

Another significant issue is the variation in teacher participation and motivation. Many teachers struggle to balance heavy administrative workloads with professional development activities, and the absence of adequate incentives further reduces engagement. Additionally, although national and regional policies demonstrate strong intent, their implementation on the ground often falls short due to technical, logistical, and communication barriers.

These ongoing challenges raise concerns about the overall effectiveness of the

competency improvement efforts. If left unaddressed, they may hinder progress toward improving education quality in the region. Therefore, a thorough and systematic study is needed to explore the factors affecting the success of teacher competency improvement programs in Kuningan Regency. This research aims not only to identify existing obstacles but also to propose effective, context-sensitive strategies for improvement.

Ultimately, the findings are expected to provide valuable insights for policy-makers and education stakeholders in designing more effective, sustainable, and impactful teacher development programs that align with local needs and conditions. Such advancements are crucial to ensuring that all teachers in Kuningan Regency can contribute optimally to the enhancement of education quality in the region.

METHODS

This study uses a qualitative descriptive approach to understand how the implementation of teacher competency improvement programs in Kuningan Regency. This approach allows researchers to explore phenomena in depth through qualitative data collection from various sources. This type of research is a case study, which aims to analyze a phenomenon in a particular context in detail. This case study focuses on the effectiveness of the teacher competency improvement program that has been implemented in Kuningan Regency, including its supporting and inhibiting factors. This method used For :

- a. Understand teacher experience in follow the improvement program competent .
- b. Analyze how this program implemented in schools .
- c. Identifying Challenges faced in program implementation .

DISCUSSION

Program Overview

The teacher competency improvement program in Kuningan Regency was developed to respond to evolving educational challenges such as diverse student needs, technological advancements, and curriculum demands. The goal is to cultivate professional, innovative teachers who serve as leaders in learning.

Implementation Stages

1. Identification of Teacher Needs

Competency needs were assessed through academic supervision, student performance analysis, and curriculum alignment.

2. Development of Training Programs

The training focused on relevant topics such as:

- a) Active learning strategies
- b) Digital literacy
- c) Character education
- d) Independent curriculum implementation

3. Training and Mentoring Implementation

Training was delivered via a blended learning approach (face-to-face and online). Mentoring was supported through Teacher Working Groups (KKG) and Subject Teacher Forums (MGMP).

4. Monitoring and Evaluation

Effectiveness was measured through:

- a) Classroom observations
- b) Teacher interviews
- c) Analysis of improvements in student learning outcomes

4.2 Enhancing Program Effectiveness

4.2.1 Improvement in Professional Competence

Teachers demonstrated improved skills in designing innovative, adaptive lessons and integrating technology like Learning Management Systems (LMS).

4.2.2 Strengthening Pedagogical Competence

Teachers improved classroom management and adopted student-centered teaching approaches tailored to diverse learning styles and needs.

4.2.3 Impact on Student Outcomes

Better teacher competence significantly enhanced student performance—shown through higher test scores, increased participation, and stronger critical/creative thinking.

4.2.4 Increased Teacher Collaboration

The program fostered stronger collaboration through KKG and MGMP, encouraging knowledge sharing and best practices that improved learning quality.

4.2.5 In-depth Impact Measurement

The program’s effectiveness was evaluated using the following quantitative and qualitative indicators:

1. Student Score Comparison (Before vs. After Training)
 - a) Example: Average student exam score increased from 70 to 78 after teacher training.
2. Feedback from Students and Parents
 - a) Student feedback showed increased satisfaction with teaching methods.
 - b) Parent interviews confirmed improved student understanding post-training.
3. Teacher Participation in Training
 - a) Out of 100 trained teachers, only 65 implemented the new methods actively in their classrooms.
4. Classroom Observation Analysis
 - a. Focused on:
 1. Use of technology-based teaching methods
 2. Teacher-student interactions
 3. Innovation in lesson delivery

Table 4.1 Comparison Before and After Training

Indicator	Before Training	After Training	Percentage Change

Average Student Exam Score	70	78	+11.4%
Student Satisfaction with Teacher Teaching	3.5/5	4.2/5	+20%
Teacher Participation Level in Training	60%	85%	+25%
Implementation of Technology in the Classroom	40% of teachers use	75% of teachers use	+35%

With this deeper impact measurement, program effectiveness can be evaluated in a more concrete and data-based manner, so that policy recommendations made are more accurate and relevant.

4.3 Program Implementation Constraints

Despite its positive impact, the program faced several challenges:

4.3.1 Facility Limitations

Many rural schools lack internet access and technological devices, making online-based training difficult to implement.

4.3.2 Varied Teacher Motivation

While many teachers showed enthusiasm, others were less committed due to workload or insufficient support from school leadership.

4.3.3 Limited Time for Implementation

Teachers struggle to attend training due to tight teaching schedules and poor teacher-student ratios in some schools.

4.3.4 Social and Psychological Factors

Non-technical factors significantly affect the program's success:

- **Gender Gap in Participation:** Female teachers, particularly in rural areas, participate less – possibly due to household responsibilities. More flexible training options are needed.
- **Administrative Burden:** 60% of teachers reported that excessive administrative tasks (like reporting, attendance tracking) limit their training participation. Support staff could help reduce this burden.
- **Support from Teacher Communities (KKG & MGMP):** Teachers involved in these communities are more motivated and better able to apply training outcomes.
- **Teacher Motivation and Satisfaction:** Recognition and incentives increase teacher engagement and creativity. Teachers without this support often revert to old methods.

4.4 Strategies to Overcome Obstacles

To address the above challenges, several strategies are proposed:

1. **Strengthening School Infrastructure:** Improve internet and technology access, especially in remote schools.
2. **Enhancing Motivation and Rewards:** Provide incentives and encourage school principals to actively support teacher participation.
3. **Flexible Training Schedules:** Offer training during holidays or via online platforms to accommodate teacher workloads.
4. **Continuous Mentoring:** Empower KKG and MGMP to serve as post-training mentoring forums.

4.5 Program Implications for Education Policy

This program provides several policy insights for Kuningan Regency:

1. **Need for Sustainability:** Programs should be ongoing and tailored to real teacher

needs.

2. **Strengthening Teacher Communities:** KKG and MGMP should be formalized as platforms for continuous professional development.
3. **Budget Allocation:** Education budgets must include funding for teacher training and supporting technological infrastructure.

4.6 Comparative Study with Other Regions

To evaluate and improve program effectiveness, the study compares Kuningan's program with similar efforts in other regions with similar geographic and demographic traits but higher success rates. This comparison helps identify best practices that can be adopted by Kuningan to enhance their teacher competency development program.

1. Comparison with Regency X (West Java) and Regency Y (Central Java)

Aspect	Regency Brass	X Regency (West Java)	Y Regency (Central Java)	Conclusion
Training Access	Limited , especially in the areas rural . Most of training Still Done in a way look at face .	Available boldly and attractively, with a more flexible schedule.	The training is conducted using a blended learning approach that utilizes LMS (Learning Management System) technology.	Kuningan needs to expand access to training to be more flexible.
Technology Support	still is constrained school internet access and	All schools have stable internet access and adequate supporting	Supported by a technology infrastructure assistance program from	The Kuningan government needs to increase

	devices technology .	devices.	the local government.	technological support in remote schools.
Teacher Participation Level	65% of teachers who participated training truly apply method new .	85% of teachers implement training results due to the monitoring and incentive system.	90% of teachers actively implement new methods, supported by a strong teacher community.	Teacher participation in Kuningan can be improved with incentives and stricter monitoring.
Incentive Patterns for Teachers	Minimum incentive for active teachers in training	There is an annual award for teachers with the best innovation in learning.	Teachers who implement the training results receive additional allowances and further learning opportunities.	Kuningan needs to implement an incentive system to increase teacher motivation.
The Role of KKG and MGMP	KKG and MGMP are active , but Not yet become an integral part of training .	KKG and MGMP are optimized as a forum for post-training mentoring.	Community-based training programs through MGMP have succeeded in increasing the implementation of training outcomes.	Kuningan can strengthen the role of KKG and MGMP as mentors for teachers.

2. Lessons from Other Regions

From comparisons with District X (West Java) and District Y (Central Java), several key takeaways can be applied in Kuningan:

- a) **Flexible Training Delivery:** Training should combine engaging in-person and online formats to reach more teachers, especially in remote areas.
- b) **Accelerated Infrastructure Development:** The local government must prioritize improving technological infrastructure, particularly in isolated schools.
- c) **Increase Teacher Participation:** Participation can be enhanced through proper incentives and improved monitoring systems.
- d) **Strengthen KKG and MGMP Roles:** These teacher communities should be reinforced as platforms for post-training mentoring and collaboration.
- e) **Introduce Recognition Programs:** Awards for innovative teachers can boost motivation and promote adoption of new teaching methods.

3. Implications for Education Policy in Kuningan Regency

- a) **Expand Access to Online Training:** More teachers in remote areas can benefit if access to online/blended learning is improved.
- b) **Allocate More Budget for Technology Infrastructure:** Budget planning should prioritize providing internet access and digital devices to schools.
- c) **Empower Teacher Communities:** KKG and MGMP should be formally included in policies as key components of continuous professional development.
- d) **Provide Incentives and Recognition:** Reward systems for teachers who adopt innovative methods can drive motivation and educational innovation.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

1. Program Effectiveness:

The program positively impacted teachers' professional and pedagogical competencies, enabling them to implement innovative, tech-integrated, and student-centered learning.

2. Enhanced Teacher Collaboration:

KKG and MGMP successfully functioned as platforms for collaboration, sharing best practices, and ongoing mentoring.

3. Impact on Student Learning Outcomes:

Students demonstrated improved participation, critical thinking, and understanding as a result of better teaching.

4. Implementation Challenges:

Obstacles included inadequate infrastructure, inconsistent teacher motivation, and limited time for training.

5. Sustainability Strategy:

Long-term success depends on improved infrastructure, flexible training schedules, empowered teacher communities, and strong policy and budget support.

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